

THE ESSENCE OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM AND THE URGENCY OF ITS FORMATION

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Annotation: From the point of view of today, the professional competence in Higher Education System is a generalized personal and special education, which includes a high the level of his theoretical and methodological, psychological and pedagogical, methodological and practical training. The professional competency means of providing a conscious solution to professional problems and the criterion for the formation of abilities.

Key words: competence, professional competence, ability, educational standards, level, skill, concept, multidimensional, theoretical level, practical level, professional activity.

Intoroduction

Competence is “a possession of a certain competency by a qualified person, including his personal attitude to it and to the subject of activity”. In other words, competence is the levels of formation of competency as a theoretical construct. Competence is a broader concept than accepted in the technique of "competency", which is traditionally understood the combination of knowledge, skills and teacher skills needed to carry out his professional activities (V.V.Safonova.).

Among the main signs of competence are the following:

- Constantly changing (with a change in the world, with a change requirements for a “successful adult”);

- focused on the future (manifested in opportunities organize your education based on your own abilities, taking into account the requirements of the future);
- has an active nature of generalized skills in combination with subject skills and knowledge in specific areas (situations);
- manifested in the ability to make choices based on self-knowledge in a particular situation;
- manifests itself in motivation for continuous self-educational activity.

Competency translated from Latin “competencia” means a circle of questions in which a person is knowledgeable has knowledge and experience. Competent in a specific area a person has relevant knowledge and abilities, allowing him to reasonably judge this area and act effectively in it. Ability as an individual psychological peculiarity of a personality is really a condition for the successful fulfillment of a certain activity.

To distinguish synonymously used concept “Competence” A. Khutorsky offers their following definitions: Competence - a set of interrelated qualities of a personality (knowledge, skills, methods of activity), set in relation to a certain range of objects and processes and necessary in order to operate efficiently and productively in relation to them.

In all areas of modern society, a serious reappraisal of past values is taking place, the content of social life and consciousness is changing, the need for highly qualified personnel capable of contributing to the progressive development of society is growing. In this regard, the professional competence of a specialist comes to the fore. A fairly large number of studies in the field of professional competency are currently being conducted as a whole (L. I. Berestova, E. N. Gusinsky and Yu. I. Turchaninova, Trfimova, V. A. Naperov, Bagramova, Khovov) and professional competence in particular (V. A. Adolf, N.V. Kuzmina, V.A.Sitarov).

Methodology

In relation to the personality of the student: reflect and develop the student's personal meanings in the direction of objects of the areas of reality he studies; characterize the activity component of education the student, the degree of his "particularity" and practical preparedness; set the minimum experience of substantive activity; develop opportunities to solve real problems in everyday life - from household to production and social; multidimensional, i.e. cover all the main groups of developed personal qualities of the student; represent the integral characteristics of the quality of student training; collectively determine and reflect the functional student literacy. In relation to knowledge, skills: associated with the ability to meaningfully apply a complex of knowledge, skills and methods of activity on an interdisciplinary range of issues; provide mastery of comprehensive educational a procedure having a personality-activity character. In relation to the structure and content of education: provide an opportunity to construct goals, the content of education (educational standards) and educational technologies in a systematic form; meta-subject, i.e. through individual elements or integrally present in various educational subjects and educational fields; multifunctional, because they allow the student to solve problems from different spheres of life; formed by means of educational content. In relation to the methods of activity: (allow you to use theoretical knowledge to solve specific problems; allow you to build clear verification meter the success of their development by students) are checked in the process of performing a specific set of actions.

Data collection and Analysis

To define the concept of "professional competence", it is initially necessary to consider the concepts of "competency"¹ and "professional competence". The most widely used definition of competence is as thorough knowledge of one's business, the essence of the work performed, complex relationships, phenomena and processes that are possible ways and means to achieve their goals. O. B. Khovov considers professional competence as a level of creative realization of

¹ Competence and competency are used as synonymy

professionalism, socio-communicative abilities and autonomy, understood as independence, law and responsibility for making independent decisions in his professional activities. N. V. Bagramova defines competency as an ability based on knowledge, educational and life experience, values and inclinations, which allows one to effectively solve problems and tasks that arise in real situations of everyday life. According to V. A. Naperov, in general, under competence personality can understand the ability of the individual to make decisions and be responsible for their implementation in various industries. The concept of competency implies combination of physical and intellectual qualities of a person and the abilities necessary for an independent and effective solution of life situations, in order to create the best conditions for oneself in a constructive interaction with others. Thus, studying professional competence as a phenomenon multidimensional, V. A. Naperov defines it at four levels:

- Theoretical (cognitive) level - a set of professional knowledge and skills acquired during professional training and practical activities.
- Practical (operational) level involves analysis structures of the need-motivational sphere of personality, professionally important personality traits.
- The creative level testifies to the growth of professional skill, its components can be considered a creative non-standard approach to solving professional problems, intellectual lability, ability to navigate in non-standard situations.

The presence of the above conditions contributes to the formation of the competence of the individual. However, one does not have to talk about stability, sustainability of competence, because it depends entirely on the flows that it is supported by the “drains” through which it is lost.²

According to I. N. Trofimova, the flows in this case are:

² E. A. Kostina. (2013) monograph “Socio-cultural competence teacher of foreign language”

- 1) The energy characteristics of the body; they change with age, as well as under the influence of biological (e.g. illness), psychological (e.g. stress or achievement of success) and social (for example, war) factors;
- 2) Informational characteristics of the environment, on the basis of which the subject forms his motivation, the range of goals and objectives everything that acts as a stimulation of his activity;
- 3) With the development of activity to achieve their goals the subject forms what his experience is - functional systems in the form of skills, assessments, attitudes and behavioral strategies.
 1. Social competence - activity in social relations demonstrate skills, mastery of skills, subjects in professional activities be able to communicate with.
 2. Special competence - the organization of professional and pedagogical activity preparation for training, rational solution of professional and pedagogical tasks, Consistently develop a realistic assessment of performance On the basis of this competence, psychological, methodological, informational, creative, innovative and communicative competence is evident.

Result

Qualities reflected on the basis of professional competence

Extreme competence Psychological, methodical, informational, creative, innovative, communicative and other competencies(deeply understands the requirements of the time; seeks new knowledge; processes them and uses them effectively in their practical activities).

- 1) psychological competence - a healthy psychological in the pedagogical process to create an environment for students and others in the learning process establishing positive communication with participants, various negative to be able to understand and resolve psychological conflicts in a timely manner;
- 2) methodical competence - methodologically of pedagogical process rational organization, correctness of forms of education or educational activity designation,

selection of methods and tools in accordance with the purpose, effective use of techniques, successful use of tools;

3) information competence - necessary, important in the information environment, search, collection, sorting, processing of necessary, useful information and their targeted, appropriate, effective use;

4) creative competence - critical, creative to pedagogical activity to be able to demonstrate his / her creative skills;

5) innovative competence - improvement of pedagogical process, improving the quality of education, the effectiveness of the educational process to put forward new ideas for improvement, to put them into practice implementation;

6) communicative competence - the whole of the educational process in sincere communication with students, including participants to be, to be able to listen to them, to be able to make a positive impact on them.

3. Personal competence - to consistent professional growth to achieve, to improve the level of qualification, their own internal in professional activities demonstrate their capabilities.

4. Technological competence - professional and pedagogical mastering advanced enrichment technologies, modern tools, access to techniques and technologies.

5. Extreme competence - emergencies (natural disasters, technological process is out of order), when pedagogical conflicts arise to make wise decisions, to have the skills to act correctly. One professional competence specific to the educator and in a number of studies its peculiarities have been studied.

6. Professional competence. Its specific aspects are wrapped.

Discussion

According to B. Nazarova's research, it is a profession on the basis of competence form the following structural bases. That, working on oneself, self-esteem in gaining professional and pedagogical competence development is important. Self-development functions through self-analysis and self-assessment determined (Yuldashev J.G', Usmonov S, 2004).

Structural bases: special two professional competencies (high level of professional activity to establish), personal competence (self-development, self-expression), individual competence (self-management, professional development and create news), social competence (joint organization of additional activities).

Summarizing the foregoing, we can conclude that talking about professional competence is only permissible in the presence of relevant knowledge, abilities, skills, the formation of the inner world of the personality - needs, settings, professional orientations and motives of activity, ideas about yourself, your professional qualities, results of own activity (Naperov V,1999, p20). In general, the formation and development of professional competencies are influenced by factors such as individual psychophysiological characteristics of the personality (innate features of the nervous system, anatomical features of the body structure, etc.), social environment (system of socio-economic relations, educational environment of the institution , reference groups), personal activity of the personality (self-education, self-education, self-development).

The concept of "competence" in the field of education entered as a result of psychologizations. Therefore competence "in unusual situations, in unexpected situations how the specialist behaves, communicates, competitors new behavior in the relationship with, uncertain tasks in execution, in the use of data full of contradictions, consistent to a plan of action in evolving and complex processes (Ochilov M.,2000).

Conclusion

To sum up, a professional competence is defined by a specialist knowledge, not the acquisition of skills, but each independent mastery of integrative knowledge and actions in the field implies Also competence specialization knowledge it is important to constantly enrich, to learn new information to understand social needs, to search for new information, requires the ability to process them and apply them in their activities. The English concept of "competence" is lexically direct Means "ability". The content is "theoretical in

action effective use of knowledge, high level of professionalism, to be able to demonstrate skills and talents”. Professional competence - professional activity by a specialist the knowledge, skills and competencies required to implement possession and application of them at a high level in practice. Based on professional competence the qualities are reflected.

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